
THE CONCEPT AND ESSENCE OF DIVERGENT THINKING IN PEDAGOGY AND PSYCHOLOGY

Tukebayeva S.,

*Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University, Almaty,
First-Year Doctoral Student*

Abitova G.

*Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University, Almaty,
PhD, Associate Professor*

ABSTRACT

The article analyses the theoretical problems of divergent thinking among preschool children with an examination of the issue of divergent thinking in pedagogical and psychological science.

Keywords: thinking, divergent thinking, convergent thinking, cognitive process.

The modern pedagogical science defines thinking as the highest stage of human cognition, reflecting objective reality. Numerous scientific theories have developed to this day, practicing various approaches to defining the essence of thinking and its development in ontogenesis. Early childhood is a unique age, and it forms the foundations for future human development at this stage of life [1].

The senior preschool age corresponds to the period of a child's life from five to seven years old; typically, at this age, a child attends the senior and preparatory groups of a kindergarten. A.V. Zaporozhets notes that between the ages of five and seven, a child attempts to understand the essence of things, the connection between phenomena, and it becomes possible to form representations and elementary concepts. The child passes on to thinking in general concepts, opens up new paths of generalization, since it occurs based on expanded object-related activities[2]. L.S. Vygotsky indicates that comprehensive concepts will only be formed through purposeful, organized engagement in active cognitive activity [3]. Among all motives of cognitive activity among pre-schoolers, emotional attitude of the child predominates, while in older pre-schoolers, even if this motive persists, other motives emerge: the motive of recognized social necessity and cognitive interest, which, under certain conditions, gains sufficient stability and activity. V.I. Loginova and P.G. Samorukova note that the conditions for the formation of cognitive activity as motives of educational cognitive activity of older pre-schoolers lie in ensuring their active position in the learning process and gradually increasing the complexity of knowledge content. New requirements are imposed on the knowledge of older pre-schoolers:

- systematic nature, i.e., the necessity of developing significant connections in matters of social life and natural phenomena;
- relative generality;
- the union of objects and phenomena based on essential characteristics.

The main changes in the activity, consciousness, and personality of the child are the emergence of the arbitrariness of mental processes – the ability to purposefully control one's behaviour and mental processes. One of the first is the associationist theory, according to which the laws of thinking development were associated with the formation and accumulation of connections (associations). Thinkers of the 18th century like

David Hume and his followers interpreted thinking as a process of accumulating associations. In accordance with the views of the Würzburg school, O. Köhler considered thinking as internal action (act), and the development of thought by representatives of this school was seen as a process of revealing relationships between opinions. The founders of Gestalt psychology, M. Wertheimer and his followers, considered thinking in the context of sudden, unprepared analytical activity aimed at identifying essential features of a problematic situation. Modern behaviourism, which emerged in the 20th century, views thinking as the adaptation of the organism to new conditions, which are a problematic situation for the organism. The theory of psychoanalysis, developed in the late 19th and early 20th centuries by the Austrian neurologist S. Freud, pays great attention to the problem of unconscious forms of thinking and its dependence on human motives and needs. Humanistic psychology, whose ideas were advanced by Swiss researcher C. Jung, points out personality traits that influence thinking (perception of reality, attitude towards reality, sense of humour). Swiss researcher J. Piaget proposed the operational concept of developing the intellect in the childhood. The theory of ontogenetic development of thinking, which emerged in the 1920s to 1940s and was developed by L.S. Vygotsky, examined the development of a child's thinking in connection with the assimilation of previously formed mental actions and operations. P.Ya. Galperin developed the theory of formation and development of intellectual operations in children, based on the idea of genetic dependence between internal intellectual operations and external practical actions. A.N. Leontiev, V.V. Davydov developed the activity theory of thinking. In this theory, thinking is considered not only as a process but also as an activity. In the late 20th century, American researcher D. Guilford formulated a theory in which two dimensions of intelligence were distinguished - convergent and divergent thinking, allowing to move away from the classical division into inductive (necessary for problem-solving, based on general rules and specific observations) and deductive (logical) thinking. Subsequently, researchers established criteria for divergent thinking and studied its role in generating unconventional ideas, hypotheses, classifications, and grouping of information. Not all questions can be resolved through sensory reflection, and then the main tool - thinking - comes into play. Thinking is the search for

answers and the quest for understanding; it engages in various types of mental activity, including observation and attention, memory and curiosity, imagination and judgment. The scientist J. Guilford first introduced the concept of "Divergent Thinking" into science. He pointed out the fundamental difference between two types of thinking operations: convergent and divergent. Divergence is defined as the ability to think in different streams, to correspond to the desired phenomenon of emergence in the broadest "space". Convergent thinking (from Lat. *Convergere* - to converge) is a form of thinking based on the strategy of precise use of previously acquired algorithms to solve a specific task; it occurs when given instructions on the sequence and content of elementary operations solve this task. Divergent thinking (from Lat. *divergere* "to diverge, deviate") is the ability of a person to generate a large number of solutions based on the same data. The line of research initiated by J. Guilford was most consistently continued by E. Torrance. The basis of the work is the opinion that processes related to problem-solving from problem identification to reporting its solution are directly related to creativity. E. Torrance includes not only specific phenomena but also characteristics associated with intelligence in the manifestations of creativity. Intersections of intelligence and creativity were found in experimental studies of creativity characteristics - fluency, flexibility, originality, and speed. Divergent thinking is not directed thinking but the ability to think widely. It provides an exit beyond the limits, beyond the framework of the initial direction of solving the problem [4]. Since there is no clearly formulated concept of divergent thinking in both domestic and foreign psychological literature, we attempted to give it our definition, which, in our opinion, most fully reflects its essential characteristic. Divergent thinking is active, exploratory, original, productive thinking, characterized by a holistic inversion discrete diverging nature. Divergent thinking is characterized by a creative approach to problem-solving, unconventional solutions, and ignoring known algorithms and patterns. Its value lies in the discovery of non-standard sequences and conclusions, in achieving original results. Just as in real life, every child's thinking in early childhood and creative talent cannot tolerate complacency and stagnation.

They exist and develop only in dynamics. The concept of divergent thinking is better known as a creative thinking process. To understand what needs to be developed to foster this type of thinking, let's enumerate the main properties of a creative approach to idea generation and development: 1) speed is the ability to formulate a maximum number of ideas; 2) flexibility is the ability to suggest a variety of ideas; 3) originality is the ability to propose unconventional ideas; 4) elaboration is the ability to give one's ideas a finished form. Research on divergent thinking has been conducted by both domestic researchers such as D.B. Bogoyavlenskaya, V.N. Druzhinin, A.M. Matyushkin, S.L. Rubinstein, E.L. Yakovleva, and others, as well as foreign researchers including De Bono, J. Guilford, A. Maslow, J. Renzulli, A. Rotenberg, E.P. Torrance, D. Filatenson, K. Heller, and others. Psychologists G. Allport and A. Maslow believed that the initial basis of creativity is the

motivation for personal growth, which does not obey the principle of pleasure; according to A. Maslow, it is the need for self-realization, the full and independent realization of one's talents and potentials in life. In the research of E. Torrance, D. Guilford, and K. Taylor, the goal of exploratory divergent thinking is emphasized as the development of investigative interest, orientation towards searching for new forms of activity that shape higher-order thinking skills. Additionally, divergent thinking activates the ability to evaluate, compare, hypothesize, analyse, and classify the obtained material. In the research of E. Renzulli and D. Filatenson, divergent thinking was considered as a fundamental trait of personality. Jean Piaget's position is interesting, as he considers divergence to be mediated by upbringing and personal experience in the autonomy of thought and action. The autonomy of divergent thinking is expressed in the ability to operate with representations by constantly adding one's own facts to judgments. For the study of divergent thinking, A.M. Matyushkin believed that the complete structure of a productive thinking act includes the generation of a problem and the formation of a thinking task, as well as the search for and justification of a solution. Representatives such as N. Gnatko and V. Druzhinin view divergent thinking as an integrative property of personality. Therefore, the various definitions of researchers and approaches to the study of the problem of divergent thinking show the existence of different positions and opinions. They have more clearly formulated the concept of divergence, established criteria for its identification, showing that this type of thinking allows a person to create ideas, hypotheses, and classifications. Thus, by analysing the literature on the research problem, it can be concluded that the development of divergent thinking plays an important role in the educational process. And in connection with this, the works by D.B. Elkonin come to mind, which claimed that play actions create a zone of proximal development of the child's cognitive sphere. Therefore, by analysing the concept of divergent thinking and the main approaches to its study, one can conclude that divergent thinking is the ability of a person to generate a large number of solutions based on the same data, a fundamentally different paradigm of mental activity based on a creative principle and the ability to paradoxical thinking, diversity of conclusions and results of the activity process. It is characterized by a creative approach to problem-solving, unconventional solutions, and ignoring known algorithms and patterns. Its value lies in the discovery of non-standard sequences and conclusions, in achieving original results.

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